

Oxidation kinetics of some sulfoxides with *N,N*-dibromobenzene sulfonamide

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of some sulfoxides with dibromamine-B yielding sulfones was investigated in presence of Hg^{II} , and the rate equation,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_3 K_2 K_h' [S]}{[RNH_2] + K_h'}$$

was found to be valid.

The reaction involves two distinct pathways namely initial fast step and a subsequent slow step. The chloride ions have no effect on the reactivity of sulfoxides. Sulfoxides containing electron-attracting substituents retard the reactivity while those containing electron-releasing constituents accelerate the rate of oxidation. Exner plot confirms the operation of same mechanism in all the sulfoxides studied. Electrophilic addition of Br^+ to sulfur atom results in an electron-deficient sulfonium centre which decomposes in a slow rate-limiting step. The rate coefficients are treated in terms of multiparametric extensions of the Hammett equation to have more insight into the mechanistic aspects.

Keywords : Kinetics, sulfoxides, sulfonamide.

Mainly *N*-haloamines are employed as analytical reagents in the estimation of variety of reactants. The information available about their kinetic behaviour in solution is meagre. We report here the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of some diaryl sulfoxides by dibromamine-B (DBB) in aqueous acetic acid medium, in the presence of Hg^{II} .

Results and discussion

The reaction involves two distinct pathways – an initial rapid step followed by a slow one for depletion of DBB. Linearity is observed only up to 45–50% of the reaction. Observed first-order rate constants decrease with increasing concentration of the oxidant (Table 1). Rate of the reaction increases proportionally with [DPSO].

Table 1. Effect of reactants on the reaction rate at 303 K

[DBB] × 10 ⁴ (mol dm ⁻³)	4.26	5.33	6.40	7.46	8.52	8.52	8.52	8.52	8.52	8.52
[SO] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	9.51	9.51	9.51	9.51	9.51	11.89	14.27	19.03	23.75	28.54
<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)	2.89	1.83	1.54	1.03	0.74	1.00	1.38	1.89	2.52	3.16
[Hg ^{II}] × 10 ⁴ (mol dm ⁻³)	0.75	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	–
<i>D</i>	56.84	56.84	56.84	56.84	64.07	56.84	49.60	42.37	35.14	–
<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)	0.90	0.74	0.95	0.78	0.55	0.74	1.07	1.77	3.16	–
[BSA] × 10 ⁴ (mol dm ⁻³)	–	2.45	3.67	4.89	7.34	9.78	–	–	–	–
<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)	2.89	2.61	2.08	1.59	1.41	1.02	–	–	–	–

Hg^{II}, a bromine scavenger has no effect on the rate. Catalytic activity of Hg^{II} in *N*-halo oxidations has been reported in some reaction systems¹⁻³. The kinetics of the reaction was observed by varying the solvent composition. The rate of the reaction increases by lowering the dielectric constant of the medium (Table 1). A plot of log *k*_{obs} against inverse of dielectric constant (*r* = 0.993; *s* = 0.039) gives a positive slope indicating the involvement of positive ions in the rate-limiting step.

The effect of ionic strength has been investigated. Acrylonitrile has no effect on the rate of sulfoxides. No ESR signals are observed indicating no free radical formation in the reaction sequence. Chloride ion has no significant effect on the reactivity of sulfoxides.

The rate constants were measured at 20°, 30° and 40°. Activation parameters are evaluated from the Eyring's plot of ln *k*₂/*T* versus 1/*T* (*r* = 0.999; *s* = 0.015) (Table 2).

The log *k*₂ values are plotted against Hammett constants - log *k*₂ versus 2σ (Fig. 1) (*r* = 0.933 ; *s* ≈ 0.359). ρ values at different temperatures are -0.99 (20°), -1.1 (30°) and -1.12 (40°). Negative ρ values imply an electron-deficient transition state. This is in agreement with the well documented nucleophilic role of sulfoxides in several oxidations. The ρ value (≈1.0) is close to the value reported for the oxidation of sulfoxides with BAB⁴.

A plot of Δ*H*[#] versus Δ*S*[#] is linear (Fig. 1) (*r* = 0.983; *s* = 3.712). Exner plot, log *k*₂(*T*₂) versus log *k*₂(*T*₁) is also linear (*r* ≈ 0.987 ; *s* ≈ 0.159). It confirms the operation of same mechanism in all the sulfoxides studied.

First-order dependence on the concentration of sulfoxide, retardation of rate by sulfonamide, positive slope of log *k*_{obs} versus 1/*D* plot and negative ρ value, all imply the following mechanism. Hg^{II} rules out bromine as the active species.

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_3 K_2 K_h' [S]}{[\text{RNH}_2] + K_h'} \quad (4)$$

where *K*_h' = *K*_h[H₂O] and "S" stands for substrate.

$$\frac{[S]}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{[\text{RNH}_2]}{k_3 K_2 K_h'} + \frac{1}{k_3 K_2} \quad (5)$$

At constant substrate concentration [S], the plot of [S]/*k*_{obs} versus [RNH₂] is linear with a significant intercept on Y axis (*r* = 0.985; *s* = 0.443) proving the validity of the rate law. Assuming the formation of intermediate in a slow step will predict a linear plot of [S]/*k*_{obs} versus [RNH₂] passing through the origin, which is contrary to experimental observations.

The first-order plots give two intersecting lines - an initial fast reaction and a subsequent slow reaction. Retardation of the rate of oxidation by benzene-sulfonamide, one of the products of the reaction, clearly confirms the above view. In Br^V oxidation of cinnamic acids⁵ slow and subsequent fast reactions are attributed to two reactive species, Br^V and molecular bromine. In the present study, two competitive reactions involving two reactive species is not ruled out. Bromine oxidation is obviated by using Hg^{II}. In acid solutions, RNHBr,

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters for the oxidation of diaryl sulfoxides with DBB

Sl. no.	Substrate	[SO] = 9.51 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³			[Hg ^{II}] = 1.00 × 10 ⁻⁴ mol dm ⁻³		
		[DBB] = 8.52 × 10 ⁻⁴ mol dm ⁻³			HOAc = 30% (v/v)		
		<i>k</i> ₂ ^a 10/dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹			Δ <i>H</i> [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-Δ <i>S</i> [#] (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>G</i> [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)
		20°	30°	40°			
1.	DPSO	1.98	3.53	6.00	39 ± 4.0	125 ± 10	76.96
2.	<i>p,p'</i> -CH ₃	2.26	6.49	15.01	69 ± 6.0	23 ± 3.0	75.54
3.	<i>p,p'</i> -OCH ₃	2.08	4.54	10.48	59 ± 5.0	56 ± 5.0	76.22
4.	<i>p,p'</i> -Cl	0.14	0.29	0.76	62 ± 6.0	69 ± 4.0	82.99
5.	<i>p,p'</i> -Br	0.08	0.16	0.32	48 ± 6.0	121 ± 14.0	84.64
6.	<i>p,p'</i> -NO ₂	0.04	0.05	0.06	20 ± 2.0	224 ± 23.0	87.79

^a*k*₂ = *k*_{obs}/[SO].

Fig. 1. The Hammett and isokinetic plots (numbered as in Table 2).

RNBr_2 and HOBr are the active species. First-order dependence on the concentration of the oxidant excludes the possibility of RNBr_2 . Kinetic observation in acidic medium very much favours RNHBr as the probable oxidising species⁶. Hydrolysis of RNHBr to give HOBr , at least to a small extent, is in agreement with first-order retardation of rate by added RNH_2 .

The kinetic data are analysed with multiparameter extensions of the Hammett equation. All four scales of σ_{R} values are used in the correlation. In all the cases, including Swain-Lupton treatment⁷, the correlation ranges from fair to satisfactory ($R = 0.94\text{--}0.98$; $\text{SE} \approx 0.3$) at all temperatures. Exner's ψ is a measure of goodness of fit, and in the Exner scale the fit is poor but under admissible limit⁸. Negative regression coefficients indicate that electron-releasing groups enhance the reactivity while electron-withdrawing ones retard the same.

$$\rho_{\text{R}}/\rho_{\text{I}} = \lambda \quad (7)$$

The values of λ (< 1) showed that the reaction is more susceptible to field effect rather than the resonance effect.

Experimental

Chloramine-B (30 g) was dissolved in water (560 ml) and liquid bromine (6 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The yellow precipitate of dibromamine-B formed was thoroughly washed with water, recrystallized from petroleum-ether, filtered and dried in vacuum⁹. With the exception of 4,4'-dinitrodiphenyl sulfoxide, all the

other diaryl sulfoxides were obtained by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of substituted benzenes with thionyl chloride¹⁰. Hydrogen peroxide oxidation of 4,4'-dinitrodiphenyl sulfide gave the corresponding sulfoxide¹⁰. All the sulfoxides were recrystallized from suitable solvents and their purities were checked.

The kinetic studies were carried out keeping sulfoxide concentration very much greater than DBB concentration. The course of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted DBB iodometrically. The reaction was followed at three different temperatures viz. 25°, 35°, 45°. The pseudo first-order rate constants, were evaluated from the slopes of the linear plots of log titre versus time. The method of least squares was adopted in all the calculations.

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

A number of reaction mixtures containing excess DBB, were kept for a day. The estimation of unreacted DBB indicated that one mol of DBB was used up for one mol of diphenyl sulfoxide.

The reaction mixtures containing excess DBB were kept aside at experimental temperature for a day or two and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with a saturated solution of sodium chloride containing 1% sodium hydroxide to remove benzene sulfonamide and the sulphone was dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate.

The solid obtained on removal of ether was crystallized from ethanol (m.p. 126 °C) indicating its authenticity.

References

1. T. S. Vivekanandam and M. S. Ramachandran, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 629.
2. S. P. Srinivasan and N. S. Gnanaprakasam, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 953.
3. S. Perumal, S. Alagumalai, S. Selvaraj and N. Arumugam, *Tetrahedron*, 1986, **42**, 4867.
4. G. Mangalam and Subbiah Meenakshisundaram, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 819.
5. C. H. Sanjeeva Reddy and E. V. Sundaram, *Tetrahedron*, 1989, **45**, 2109.
6. B. Timme Gowda and D. S. Mahadevappa, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1983, 323.
7. J. Shorter, "Similarity Models in Organic Chemistry, Biochemistry and Related Fields", eds. R. I. Zalewski, T. N. Krygowski and J. Shorter, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1991.
8. J. Shorter, "Correlation Analysis in Organic Reactivity", Research Studies, Chichesder, 1982.
9. D. S. Mahadevappa and M. S. Ahmed, *Talanta*, 1979, **26**, 590.
10. H. J. Shine, M. Rahman, H. Seeger and G. S. Wu, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1901, **32**, 1967.